

earlier and accordingly there are only terminal groups in the compounds reported here. Turco⁸ has distinguished between frequencies for M-SCN and M-NCS compound. The compounds reported here seem to possess M-NCS groups.

Further infrared spectra of the complexes show strong absorption bands of both the tetramethyl ammonium ion (745 cm⁻¹ and 970 cm⁻¹) and the ligands. The shifting of ligand absorption bands as seen in the infrared spectra of the complexes are indicative of definite metal ligand bonding.

The complexes having the formula [Me₄N]₂[Zn(SCN)₄L₂] where L is pyridine, 4-methyl pyridine and isoquinoline, seem to have hexa coordination, whereas the complexes [Me₄N]₂[Zn(SCN)₄L] where L = quinoline and thiourea are possibly penta coordinated. The exact coordination number can be established only by X-ray studies.

Acknowledgements

Thanks are due to Prof. D. V. Raman Rao for recording the infrared spectra and to Prof. P. C. Brahma for his interest in the work.

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Determination of Bismuth with Ammonium Phenylthiocarbamate as a Gravimetric Reagent

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Manuscript received 2 January 1976, revised 16 August 1976,
accepted 30 December 1976

MUSIL and Hass¹ studied the analytical characteristics of ammonium phenylthiocarbamate. The reagent has proved useful for many of the sulphide forming cations. The present report records the results of the gravimetric determination of bismuth(III) which is precipitated quantitatively in the pH range 0.8 to 6.3. Many a organic precipitant²⁻⁶ has been suggested for the gravimetric determination of bismuth. The use of the present reagent, however, is advantageous in certain respects. The reagent is very easily prepared, readily soluble in water and stable in the solid form. The bismuth complex is of definite composition and hence directly weighable. The complex, though unstable in the hot acid medium, is sufficiently granular and easily filterable at room temperature. In the presence of

EDTA the procedure is appreciably selective for the determination of bismuth. The following structure of the bismuth complex formed is suggested from its analytical data.

Experimental

Bismuth(III) Solution: Bismuth Nitrate pentahydrate (3.5262 g) of B.D.H. quality was dissolved in 1 litre of distilled water and acidified with nitric acid. Bismuth was determined as pyrogallate⁷. An aliquot was then suitably diluted to prepare a 0.1% solution of the metal.

Reagent Solution: Aqueous solution of the reagent (1.0%) prepared freshly was used for the determination.

Determination of Bismuth: Twenty five ml. of the bismuth solution was taken in a 500 ml beaker and diluted to about 130 ml. Ammonium Nitrate (2.5 g) and ten ml. of sodium potassium tartrate (10%) were added; the pH of the solution was adjusted between 5 to 6 by the addition of sodium acetate solution (10%). The reagent solution was then introduced dropwise with continuous stirring of the contents of the beaker. The yellow precipitate thus obtained was further stirred for about 10 mins. and then allowed to stand for half an hour. It was then filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G3), washed with water, and dried to a constant weight at 100° in about one and a quarter hours. The results are recorded in Table 1. The weight of the precipitate multiplied by 0.2754 gives the weight of bismuth.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF BISMUTH(III) IN PRESENCE OF DIVERSE IONS (25 mg of Bismuth taken for each determination)

Diverse ion	Added as	Amount added mg.	Bi Complex mg.	Bi found mg.	Error mg.
—	—	—	90.9	25.03	+0.03
—	—	—	90.7	24.98	-0.02
—	—	—	90.7	24.98	-0.02
—	—	—	90.8	25.00	0.00
K(I)	Nitrate	100	91.4	25.17	+0.17
Ca(II)	Chloride	100	91.8	25.27	+0.27
Be(II)	Nitrate	100	90.5	24.92	-0.08
Sr(II)	Nitrate	100	90.9	25.03	+0.03
Mg(II)	Nitrate	100	91.9	25.30	+0.30
Mn(II)	Chloride	100	91.4	25.17	+0.17
Zn(II)	Chloride	100	90.2	24.84	-0.16
Al(III)	Acetate	100	90.7	24.98	-0.02
Cr(III)	Acetate	100	90.7	24.98	-0.02
Fe(III)*	Ferric Alum	50	91.3	25.14	+0.14
Fe(II)*	Mohr's Salt	50	90.9	25.03	+0.03
Co(II)*	Nitrate	50	90.0	24.78	-0.22
Ni(II)*	Nitrate	50	90.9	25.03	+0.03
Pb(II)*	Nitrate	50	91.4	25.17	+0.17
Cd(II)*	Sulphate	50	91.4	25.17	+0.17
Zr(IV)	Nitrate	50	91.3	25.14	+0.14
Tungstate	Sodium	50	90.9	25.03	+0.03

* Masked with EDTA.

Determination of bismuth in presence of diverse ions: The procedure for the determination of bismuth in the presence of diverse ions is the same as described above except that the pH of the solution was adjusted after the addition of a diverse ion. Alkali metals, alkaline earths, ammonium, Zn(II), Mn(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Zr(IV) and tungstate do not interfere with the determination and Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(II), Fe(III), Pb(II) and Cd(II) can be masked with EDTA. Ag(I), Hg(II), Cu(II) and Sb(III) interfere with the determination. The results are recorded in Table 1. The tolerance of the diverse ions has been studied only upto the amounts mentioned in the table.

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Studies on Lanthanide DAMO-SAO Mixed Complexes

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Manuscript received 9 July 1976, revised 19 December 1976,
accepted 30 December 1976

SEVERAL Lanthanide simple oximates¹⁻⁵ and mixed complexes where oximes are used as primary ligands and 1,10-phenanthroline, oxine and pyridine-2, aldoxime as the second ligand were prepared and characterised⁶. This communication details the preparation and characterisation of certain Lanthanide mixed complexes using DAMO as primary ligand and SAO as second ligand.

The simple Lanthanide diacetylmonoximate were prepared by the method reported by Rao *et al.*⁵. Mixed complexes were prepared adopting the following procedure.

A weighed quantity of Lanthanide diacetylmonoximate was dissolved in ethanol and mixed with a calculated amount (Mole Ratio 1 : 3) of Salicylal-doxime. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.8 by addition of alcoholic ammonia. The resulting solution was evaporated on a steam bath when the solid separated. The excess ligand was washed with ether. All the compounds were vacuum dried over fused calcium chloride for 48 hrs. Analytical data of the mixed complexes is detailed in Table 1. The conductivity data of the compounds indicated that they are all non electrolytes.

Results and Discussion

The ligand DAMO has a band in u.v. region around 220 nm (log $\epsilon = 4.04$) and SAO has two bands at 260 nm (log $\epsilon = 4.22$) and 305 nm (log $\epsilon = 3.78$). Both the ligand bands have been located in the mixed complexes with a change in log ϵ values as compared with free ligand values. The change gives an indication of the existence of both the ligands in the complexes and of their strong interaction with lanthanide ions.

In the visible region the characteristic band of Pr³⁺ and Sm³⁺ ions could not be located in this investigation. Only the 576 nm band of Nd³⁺ ion is located, with a red shift, around 580-585 nm (log $\epsilon = 1.49$). This red shift can, as a first approximation be correlated with (i) dsp hybridisation, (ii) possible involvement of 4f electrons in chelation, and (iii) strong interaction of Nd³⁺ ion with the ligands.

In the i.r. region the ligand DAMO exhibits two bands around 3410 cm⁻¹ and 3350 cm⁻¹ due to OH stretch of the oxime. SAO exhibits only one band at 3350 cm⁻¹ and is assigned to the presence of the oxime group with probably intramolecular hydrogen bonding. In the lanthanide salicylal-doximates reported⁵ the 3350 cm⁻¹ band has suffered a negative shift in some cases while it disappeared in the rest.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF LANTHANIDE COMPLEXES

Complex	% Metal		% Chloride		% Nitrogen	
	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.
Y(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	22.39	22.29	17.88	17.50	6.97	6.80
La(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	31.08	30.09	15.88	15.00	6.26	6.02
Pr(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	31.37	31.20	15.82	15.60	6.23	6.20
Nd(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	31.87	31.27	15.70	15.50	6.189	5.99
Sm(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	32.78	32.50	15.48	15.40	6.105	6.08
Gd(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	33.77	33.34	15.25	15.00	6.015	6.00
Dy(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	34.52	33.90	15.09	14.95	5.95	5.80